

**Reactions of 3-Arylimino-2*H*-indol-2-ones with
o-Mercaptobenzoic Acid and Salicylic Acid :
Synthesis of Novel Spiro[2*H*-1,3-benzothiazine-2,3'-[3*H*]indole]-2,4(1'*H*,3*H*)-diones**

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DIVERSE types of biological activities are displayed by indole derivatives¹, benzothiazines² and benzoxazines³. In view of this and in order to synthesise potent pharmacophores incorporating the indole and benzothiazine/benzoxazine moieties, the present reactions were investigated.

In continuation to our earlier work⁴, the reactions of 3-arylimino-2*H*-indol-2-ones with *o*-mercaptobenzoic acid and its oxygen containing analogue, salicylic acid are reported.

The reaction of 3, obtained from suitably substituted isatins and anilines, with *o*-mercaptobenzoic acid in acidic alcohol under reflux yielded a novel

spiro system, spiro[2*H*-1,3-benzothiazine-2,3'-[3*H*]-indole]-2',4(1'*H*,3*H*)-dione.

In a parallel reaction with salicylic acid instead of the expected spiro[2*H*-1,3-benzoxazine-2,3'-[3*H*]-indole]-2',4(1'*H*,3*H*)-dione, we obtained *O*-[3-(1,3-dihydro-2-oxo-(2*H*)indolyl)]salicylic acid (5) by the loss of an iminophenyl moiety (Scheme 1). The formation of this compound and not the spiro derivative can be explained on the basis of the fact that in case of salicylic acid hydrolysis of the 'anil' occurred before cyclocondensation due to lower acidity of the OH group as compared to the SH. The structural assignments were based on spectral data.

1-5 a; R=R'=H, b; R=H, R'=CH₃, c; R=CH₃, R'=H
Scheme 1

Results and Discussion

The ir spectrum of compound 3a revealed characteristic peaks at 3 320 (N-H), 1 680 (C=O) and 1 620 cm⁻¹ (C=N stretching). The ¹H nmr spectrum displayed signals at δ 6.80-7.85 (9H, m, ArH) and 9.80 (1H, s, NH). Compound 4 showed the ir peaks at 1 700 and 1 680 (C=O), 1 100 (C-N), 680-700 (C-S-C-) and the absence of the peak at 1 620 cm⁻¹ (C=N) which was present in 3. The band at 3 320 cm⁻¹ (N-H) was retained. The ¹H nmr spectrum exhibited peaks at δ 7.17-8.24 (13H,

m, ArH) and 10.0 (1H, s, NH). The mass spectral analysis showed the molecular ion peak at *m/z* 358 (4a) corresponding to the molecular formula C₂₁H₁₄N₂O₂S. The ir spectrum of 5 revealed a broad band at 2 700-3 560 (OH stretching, COOH), 3 060-3 265 (N-H superimposed on OH), 1 700 (acidic C=O), 1 675 (imide C=O) and 1 185 cm⁻¹ (C-O-C). The ¹H nmr singlets at δ 5.21 and 9.20 were assigned to the CH and N protons respectively. Additional signals were observed at 6.62-7.65 (8H, m, ArH) and a broad singlet at 10.95 (OH). The molecular ion peak at *m/z* 269 (5a) corresponding to C₁₅H₁₁NO₄, further confirmed the proposed structure. The hydrolysis of the anil moiety was further confirmed by the absence of a signal for CH₃ group in the ¹H nmr spectrum of 5b obtained from 3-(methylphenylimino)-2*H*-indol-2-one.

Experimental

M.ps. are uncorrected and the purity of the samples was checked by tlc. The ir spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 577 spectrophotometer, ¹H nmr spectra (DMSO-d₆; TMS as an internal standard) on a Jeol FX-90Q instrument (89.55 MHz), and mass spectra on a Kratos-30 and 50 mass spectrometers. All compounds gave satisfactory results for elemental analysis for N and S.

4,5-Dihydro-3-phenyl-spiro[2*H*-1,3-benzothiazine-2,3'-[3*H*]-indole]-2',4(1'*H*,3*H*)-diones (4a): A mixture of 3-phenylimino-2*H*-indol-2-one (2.22 g, 0.01 mol) and *o*-mercaptobenzoic acid (1.54 g, 0.01 mol) was refluxed in absolute ethanol-glacial acetic acid (50 : 10) for 10 h. The resulting solid was recrystallised from ethanol to give 4a (78%), m.p. 285-87°. Other compound were similarly prepared: 4b (71%), 280°; 4c (74%), 274°.

***O*-[3-(1,3-Dihydro-2-oxo-(2*H*)indolyl)]salicylic acid (5a):** A mixture of 3-phenylimino-2*H*-indol-2-one (2.22 g, 0.01 mol) and salicylic acid (1.38 g, 0.01 mol) was refluxed in absolute ethanol-glacial acetic acid (50 : 10) for 10 h. The resulting solid was dried and recrystallised from ethanol to give 5a (75%), m.p. 300°. In a similar manner other compounds were prepared: 5b (70%), m.p. 300°; 5c (72%), 292-94°.

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NOTES

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